

Measurement-based Analysis of Multi-band Assisted Beam-forming at mmWave in Industrial Scenarios

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Abstract—The mmWave and sub-THz bands are foreseen as candidates to achieve the data-rate demands in the beyond 5G and 6G wireless communication networks. The co-existence of multiple radio interfaces at several bands enables data fusion and the utilization of the similarities and differences on propagation and system properties for communication and sensing applications. MmWave radio interfaces rely on directive beams that require high training overhead for beam steering. Sensors in the network infrastructure and co-located radio interfaces at sub-6 GHz and mmWave can be used to assist the beam-forming process at mmWave. In the present paper we investigate the performance of multi-band assisted beam-forming in an industrial environment. We empirically demonstrate from real-world measurements that even in NLOS, the direction of the beams estimated at sub-6 GHz can be used to establish a link at mmWave.

Index Terms—Channel sounding, mmWave, beam-forming, ICAS, industry 4.0.

I. INTRODUCTION

The large blocks of free spectrum at mmWave and in the lower THz bands offer the possibility to reach the expected demands of data-rates in the future wireless communication networks. The co-existence of multiple radio interfaces operating at different frequencies, co-located or distributed, give birth to heterogeneous networks that can be benefited from the differences on characteristics in propagation (e.g., penetration loss, coverage, reflectivity, etc.) and systems aspects (larger bandwidth and higher directivity) [1]. Hence, a joint exploitation of the different resources in the framework of integrated communications and sensing (ICAS), joint radar and communication system (JRCS), and simultaneous localization and mapping (SLAM) opens a wide spectrum of possibilities for new services and applications [2], [3].

The increased isotropical path-loss at mmWave requires the utilization of highly directive radio interfaces that need to be steered in the direction of the relevant paths. Thus, communication systems must know where to point the antenna gain. However, obtaining this information with phased-array-based analog mmWave beam-forming is time consuming since there is a trade off between range and directivity: while sharper beams cover larger distances requiring more time to train and scan the environment, the opposite happens with broader beams. A compromise is the two-step approach in which a coarse estimation is followed by a fine tuning. Yet, this is still

Figure 1. Example of a UE in NLOS communicating to a BS with co-located radio interfaces at sub-6 GHz and mmWave. Differences on propagation characteristics originate different optimum beam directions. Picture at Bosch factory in Blaichach.

time consuming and not optimum in highly dynamic time-variant scenarios.

In that regard, the integration of sensing services in the network can assist the estimation process and facilitate beam-forming at mmWave [4]. In this case, the network is equipped with multiple sensors in charge of estimating the position of the user equipment (UE). With this information, the base station (BS) can calculate the steering angles for the beam-former. However, blockage in dynamic scenarios or NLOS positions can originate severe losses if there is not a map of the environment with the visibility information.

A different approach is the case of co-located sub-6 GHz and mmWave radio interfaces at the BS and UE, as shown in Fig. 1. In this case, the network can estimate the mmWave beam-steering direction with the information collected from

the sub-6 GHz link. Since sub-6 GHz does not rely on phased-arrays but on fully digital architectures, similar accuracy can be obtained with less overhead on the training phase. Early studies have already been presented from measurements in V2V scenarios in [5] and from simulations in [6]. The advantage of the co-located multi-band method compared to a distributed estimation of the steering direction (as the sensor based), is that the co-location ensures (at least at sub-6 GHz) a connecting electromagnetic path between the BS and the UE. In LOS, there is no difference on the connecting path in the different frequencies. However, since propagation characteristics as penetration or diffraction loss are larger at mmWave, it might be the case that certain paths at sub-6 GHz are not present at mmWave in NLOS, and therefore there is a considerable loss on the achievable RX power compared to steering a beam in the direction estimated at mmWave, specially in high scattering environments as the industrial one.

Therefore, the study of the similarities and differences on propagation at sub-6 GHz and mmWave in complex scenarios is of critical importance to validate this method. In that regard, simultaneous multi-band measurements have been conducted in indoor [7], V2V [5], outdoor [8], and industry [9], [10] scenarios, showing in all cases a similarity on the strongest specular multi-path components (MPCs) at sub-6 GHz and mmWave in the different visibility conditions. The main differences were related to the amount of dense multipath component (DMC), [9]. However, it is also important to consider that depending on the beam-width and directivity of the radio interface, a beam steered in the direction of the strongest path can still deliver less power than a beam steered in the direction of multiple weaker paths.

In this paper we empirically analyze the performance of a beam-former from measurements at mmWave considering the steering direction obtained from a co-located sub-6 GHz radio interface in an industrial scenario, with special focus in the NLOS case. We consider realistic antenna patterns with broad beams and fixed possible steering directions. The performance is evaluated by comparing the achieved RX power at mmWave when the beam is steered into the direction of the stronger beam at sub-6 GHz with the RX power obtained when the beam is steered in the direction that delivers maximum power at mmWave.

II. MULTI-BAND ASSISTED BEAM-FORMING

A. System Model

The system consists of a fixed BS and a mobile UE (e.g. a robot, self-driven trolley, etc.). Both are equipped with co-located radio interfaces at sub-6 GHz (6.75 GHz) and mmWave (33.75 GHz), as shown in Fig. 2. The BS can steer 30° half-power beam-width (HPBW) beams in azimuth and elevation with $\Delta\phi = \Delta\theta = 30^\circ$ steps in fixed directions from a code-book. The UE has an isotropic antenna pattern.

The RX signal $\mathbf{Y}^b(f) \in \mathbb{C}^{I \times J}$ after TX beam-steering in the frequency band $b = \{\text{sub6}, \text{mmW}\}$ can be formulated as

$$\mathbf{Y}_{i,j}^b(f) = \mathbf{G}_{i,j}^b(f, \phi, \theta) \mathbf{H}^b(f, \phi, \theta) \mathbf{S}^b(f) + \mathbf{N}_{i,j}^b(f), \quad (1)$$

Figure 2. System model with multi-band phased-array beam steering at the BS and isotropic radiator at the UE in a NLOS position.

where $N_{i,j}^b \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu, \sigma)$ is additive white Gaussian noise, $S^b(f)$ is the spectrum of the TX signal, $H^b(f, \phi, \theta)$ is the frequency response (FR) of the multi-dimensional channel considering isotropic radiators, and $G_{i,j}^b(f, \phi, \theta)$ is the resulting TX pattern after beam steering $G^b(f, \phi, \theta)$ in the $i\Delta\phi$ azimuth and $j\Delta\theta$ elevation directions:

$$G_{i,j}^b(f, \phi, \theta) = \sum_{i,j} G^b(f, \phi, \theta) * \delta(\phi - i\Delta\phi) * \delta(\theta - j\Delta\theta). \quad (2)$$

The total RX power $\mathbf{P}^b \in \mathbb{R}^{I \times J}$ in the different pointing directions (i, j) in the band b is calculated as

$$P_{i,j}^b = \sum_{\forall f} |Y_{i,j}^b(f)|^2. \quad (3)$$

The optimum steering direction $i_o^{\text{sub6}}, j_o^{\text{sub6}}$ at sub-6 GHz is determined as the beam that delivers more power to the RX,

$$P_{i_o^{\text{sub6}}, j_o^{\text{sub6}}}^{\text{sub6}} \geq P_{i,j}^{\text{sub6}} \quad \forall (i_o^{\text{sub6}}, j_o^{\text{sub6}}) \neq (i, j). \quad (4)$$

Similarly, the optimum steering direction (benchmark) $(i_o^{\text{mmW}}, j_o^{\text{mmW}})$ at mmWave is determined as

$$P_{i_o^{\text{mmW}}, j_o^{\text{mmW}}}^{\text{mmW}} \geq P_{i,j}^{\text{mmW}} \quad \forall (i_o^{\text{mmW}}, j_o^{\text{mmW}}) \neq (i, j), \quad (5)$$

and is equal to the result of scanning in all the possible directions and selecting the one that delivers the maximum power.

B. Multi-band Assisted Beam-forming

In this case, the beam-steering direction at mmWave is the optimum beam-steering direction at sub-6 GHz $(i_o^{\text{sub6}}, j_o^{\text{sub6}})$. Hence, the RX power at mmWave is calculated as

$$P_{i_o^{\text{sub6}}, j_o^{\text{sub6}}}^{\text{mmW}} \leq P_{i_o^{\text{mmW}}, j_o^{\text{mmW}}}^{\text{mmW}}. \quad (6)$$

The upper bound of the algorithm is $P_{i_o^{\text{mmW}}, j_o^{\text{mmW}}}^{\text{mmW}}$. Therefore, the performance is evaluated based on difference of the algorithm to the benchmark:

$$L_{\text{MBA}} = P_{i_o^{\text{mmW}}, j_o^{\text{mmW}}}^{\text{mmW}} - P_{i_o^{\text{sub6}}, j_o^{\text{sub6}}}^{\text{mmW}}. \quad (7)$$

In the best case, $P_{i_o^{\text{sub6}}, j_o^{\text{sub6}}}^{\text{mmW}} = P_{i_o^{\text{mmW}}, j_o^{\text{mmW}}}^{\text{mmW}}$, meaning that the steering directions at sub-6 GHz and mmWave are the same and there are no losses after applying the multi-band assisted beam-forming algorithm.

C. Sensor Aided Beam-forming

In the sensor aided case, the optimum steering direction $(i_o^{\text{sens}}, j_o^{\text{sens}})$ is geometrically determined accordingly to the 3D coordinates of the BS and UE. While the first ones are known to the network, the coordinates of the UE are determined by either dedicated sensors in the infrastructure, or by other BSs with LOS to the UE. The RX power is then calculated as

$$P_{i_o^{\text{sens}}, j_o^{\text{sens}}}^{\text{mmW}} \leq P_{i_o^{\text{mmW}}, j_o^{\text{mmW}}}^{\text{mmW}}. \quad (8)$$

Similarly to (7), the performance is evaluated based on the difference to the benchmark

$$L_{SA} = P_{i_o^{\text{mmW}}, j_o^{\text{mmW}}}^{\text{mmW}} - P_{i_o^{\text{sens}}, j_o^{\text{sens}}}^{\text{mmW}}. \quad (9)$$

Statistical results of the multi-band assisted and sensor aided beam-forming process algorithm based on the application loss $L_{MBA/SA}$ are presented in Section IV.

III. EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP

A. Scenario

The scenario consists of a production hall by Bosch in Blaichach, Germany. While the dimensions of the complete hall are $171 \text{ m} \times 74 \text{ m} \times 16 \text{ m}$ ($L \times W \times H$), the measurements were conducted within an area of $42 \text{ m} \times 46 \text{ m} \times 16 \text{ m}$. As shown in the composite picture taken from the different angular scans at the TX in Fig. 3, there are three production lines and a storage area. Together with the RF measurements, 3D point-cloud data was collected to develop a ray-tracing model of the scenario presented in [11], [12].

The measurements emulate a scenario with a BS with co-located radio interfaces at sub-6 GHz and mmWave, positioned in the top of a production unit connected to a gateway supporting the complete production cell. The UE, also with co-located radio interfaces, is moving in the different corridors. The RF channel is sampled at some positions on the track.

B. Measurement Set-up

The TUIL dual-polarized multi-band channel sounder simultaneously measures up to three different bands with a null-to-null measurement bandwidth of 6.75 GHz, [13]. The measured center frequency of the different bands were 6.75 GHz (covering the sub-6 GHz spectrum), 33.75 GHz, and 60.75 GHz (for sake of simplicity, labeled as sub-6 GHz, 30 GHz, and 60 GHz, respectively). This paper focuses only in the sub-6 GHz and 30 GHz bands. The sounding excitation signal was a 15-bit maximum length binary sequence (MLBS), covering an unambiguity range in propagation distance of $\approx 1455 \text{ m}$.

The angular domain was scanned at the TX using a single 30° HPBW horn antennas mounted over a positioner at 4.2 m height (above clutter level) scanning from -90° to 90° in azimuth and from -60° to 30° in elevation with 30° steps, emulating the beam-steering process of the BS. At the RX side, also a single custom dipole antenna with quasi-omni-directional pattern was used at 1.36 m height. The environment was static during the measurements.

The RX, emulating an UE, was located in a line over 4 different tracks, namely, L1, L2, L3, and L4, as shown in

Fig. 3. L1 and L2 were mostly in NLOS: L1 is obstructed by a large metal shaft and two production lines and L2 is in between two production lines. L3 and L4 are pure LOS tracks. The RX was placed in 0.5 m steps over these lines covering in average 24 m length. However, due to different circumstances not all the measurement positions are available for analysis. More details on the measurement set-up and the analysis of the propagation characteristics in this scenario can be found in [10].

C. Pre-processing of the Measurements

The measurements are recorded in the time domain and collected in a multi-dimensional array with the same structure as the system model in (1). The noise floor was estimated in the time domain independently per band and angular scan and removed with a cut-off margin of 10 dB. In addition, the dynamic range of the channel impulse response (CIR) was limited to 20 dB to emulate characteristics of real communication systems. Thus, the measured power from the channel in every angular scan corresponds to the measured RX signal power described in (3).

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

An example of the power azimuth/elevation profile at 30 GHz seen from the BS with the UE in the NLOS marked position in L1 behind a metal shaft is shown in Fig. 4. The normalized power of the different beams at 30 GHz is coded in colors, and the direction of the optimum beam at sub-6 GHz $(i_o^{\text{sub6}}, j_o^{\text{sub6}})$ is displayed with a cross (\times), the direction of the optimum beam at 30 GHz $(i_o^{\text{mmW}}, j_o^{\text{mmW}})$ with a plus sign (+), and the direction of the beam estimated geometrically from the sensors $(i_o^{\text{sens}}, j_o^{\text{sens}})$ in circle (\circ).

In this particular case, there is a mismatch between the beam with maximum power at sub-6 GHz and 30 GHz, as shown in Fig. 5a and Fig. 5b, respectively. The reason could be a stronger diffracted component or more MPCs at sub-6 GHz than at 30 GHz in the direction $(i_o^{\text{sub6}}, j_o^{\text{sub6}}) = (-90^\circ, -30^\circ)$. At 30 GHz, the optimum beam is in the direction $(i_o^{\text{mmW}}, j_o^{\text{mmW}}) = (-30^\circ, 0^\circ)$ towards the machinery, as can be seen in Fig. 4.

A different case in NLOS is displayed in Fig. 5c and Fig. 5d, where the direction of the optimum beams coincide at sub-6 GHz and 30 GHz at $(i_o^{\text{sub6}}, j_o^{\text{sub6}}) = (i_o^{\text{mmW}}, j_o^{\text{mmW}}) = (-30^\circ, 0^\circ)$. In this case, there is no losses on applying at mmWave the directional information obtained from the sub-6 GHz.

A third example is in LOS, presented in Fig. 5e and Fig. 5f. The UE goes from NLOS (behind the metal shaft) to a short period in LOS, and then in NLOS behind the production line while displacing along L1. As expected, in this case the optimum beam direction is the same at sub-6 GHz and mmWave. However, the sensor estimated is still in and adjacent beam due to quantization of the steering angles.

Finally, Fig. 5g and Fig. 5h show the NLOS case in which the multi-band assisted and the sensor aided coincide with the optimum at mmWave.

Figure 3. Composite picture from the TX towards the production line. In red markers, the NLOS RX positions and in green, the RX LOS positions.

Figure 4. Example of worst case scenario from the measurements in NLOS when the RX is behind a metal shaft (real location in red circle): best beam direction at sub-6 GHz in (x) differs to the maximum power beam direction at 30 GHz (+) and the beam direction from the real location (o). In the background, the measured power azimuth/elevation profile (power per beam) in the different directions at 30 GHz.

The cumulative distribution function (CDF) of the difference to the benchmark $L_{MBA/SA}$ obtained with the multi-band assisted and the sensor aided beam-forming considering all the measured locations in L1, L2, L3, and L4 separated in LOS and NLOS is displayed in Fig. 6.

In NLOS, in the 90% of the cases the multi-band assisted beam-forming outperforms the sensor aided beam-forming process, since the differences to the benchmark are lower than 1.4 dB and 3.7 dB, respectively. This can be explained due to the fact that the multi-band assisted beam-forming process ensures that there is an electromagnetic path (composed by multiple MPCs) between the BS and the UE in the selected beam, at least at a different carrier frequency. It might not be the optimum, since this is calculated at sub-6 GHz where there are stronger diffracted path and more DMC than at mmWave,

however, as seen in the results, the differences are not so critical. On the other hand, a beam pointed in the NLOS direction of the UE (geometrically estimated) will be severely affected by the penetration loss. Considering a cut on the 99% of the cases, the multi-band method still outperforms the sensor aided method by a difference of 2 dB.

In LOS, the sensor aided and multi-band methods have 0 dB differences to the benchmark in the 90% of the cases. However, considering the 99%, the sensor aided method slightly outperforms the multi-band assisted beam-former by 0.14 dB.

The CDF considering all the cases without separating LOS and NLOS (since alternating the methods accordingly to the visibility would require that knowledge) shows that the multi-band approach outperforms the sensor aided by 1.48 dB in the 90% of the cases, and by 2.1 dB in the 99% of the cases.

Figure 5. Power azimuth/elevation profile at sub-6 GHz and 30 GHz for different positions and visibility conditions of the UE in L1. The diamond represents the current location, the line all the possible locations in L1, the plus sign the optimum at mmWave, the cross the optimum at sub-6 GHz, and the circle the sensor estimated beam direction.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper we have presented the results from a rich set of real-world measurements in a factory showing that there are minimal losses, in NLOS, compared to the benchmark (selecting the strongest beam after scanning all the possibilities) when the beams at mmWave are steered using the directional information derived from a co-located sub-6 GHz radio interface. The results outperformed the method of steering the beams into the direction of the real location of the UE, obtained from sensors in the network. This facilitates the beam steering process at mmWave by reducing training time and also offers robustness for communications in NLOS conditions.

These results depend on the beam-width of the radio interface and the TX-RX distances, limited in this analysis to the available experimental data. Different beam-widths will be

Figure 6. Empirical CDF of the difference on RX power compared to the benchmark (scanning all the possible beams at mmWave and selecting the stronger one) after applying multi-band or sensor aided beam-forming.

addressed in simulations from ray-tracing in the same scenario in future publications.

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